

Two Slit Interference and a Physical Interpretation of Interaction Momentum

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The two slit interference equations are given by $d \sin(\theta) = n \text{ wavelength}$ (for maxima) and $d \sin(\theta) = (n+0.5) \text{ wavelength}$ (for minima) where d is the distance between slit centers and θ is measured from the y axis with the slits lying along the x (1). These results may be readily obtained by writing intensity proportional to $|\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_1) + \exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_2)|^2$ ((1)) and assuming that \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 are parallel with each ray emerging from the center of each slit.

We try to explain this result by suggesting that $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ is linked to interactions (i.e. to momentum and interactions). Thus, the interaction which occurs in the 2-slit problem is with (p_x) (x component of \mathbf{p}) over the range of d . In order to see quantum effects, one expects $(kx) d \approx 2\pi$. From this, one obtains again $d \sin(\theta) = \text{wavelength}$ for $n=1$. In other words, $\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$ is used for calculations, but there is an underlying physical scenario directly linked to the specific interaction which occurs, we argue.

Signal Special Relativistic Approach to $\exp(ipx)$

We have argued that $\exp(ipx)$ ($\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r})$) follows from the special relativistic Lorentz invariant

$$-Et + px = \text{constant} \neq 0 \quad ((2)) \quad (\text{for a particle with rest mass } m_0)$$

Even though the constant in ((2)) is not 0, there are signals in the rest mass, linked with interactions, and traveling with speed c in all frames, and we argue that like a free photon, they are linked with:

$$-E \Delta t + p \Delta x = 0 \rightarrow \Delta t = \text{constant}/E \text{ and } \Delta x = \text{constant}/p \quad ((3))$$

To be consistent with a free photon, $\text{constant} = \hbar$ ((4)).

We wish to stress that these signals are linked with an interaction and this also involves E and p . If one has a particle with rest mass moving with p_1 , it may interact with a 2-slit apparatus at rest and or with one that is moving with a constant speed. The moving one has momentum and in an interaction, one must consider the sum of momenta. For the 2-slit apparatus at rest, one may use the wavelength linked with p_1 as being associated with slit widths, but for the moving one, one should go into its rest frame and calculate p_2 . This then yields the appropriate wavelength linked to slit separation. In other words, Δx is linked to the relative momentum of interaction.

We note that a function consistent with this idea is:

$$\exp(p x) \text{ because } \exp(i p_1 x) \exp(i p_2 x) = \exp(i (p_1+p_2) x) \quad ((5))$$

Here p_1 and p_2 may be positive or negative and so one needs a net momentum in order to find the correct wavelength.

Solving the Two Slit Problem Using $\exp(ipx)$

Here we use $p = \hbar k$ with $\hbar=1$ and $k = 2\pi/\text{wavelength}$.

One may use: intensity proportional to $|\exp(ip \cdot r_1) + \exp(ip \cdot r_2)|^2$ ((6))

r_1 is an r vector from the center of slit 1, and r_2 , from the center of slit 2. If a screen is very far away from the slits, the traditional approximation is to state that r_1 and r_2 are parallel. Let θ be an angle measured from the y axis with the slits along the x . Then $p \cdot r_1 - p \cdot r_2 = p d \sin(\theta)$.

((6)) yields: $2 + 2 \cos(p d \sin(\theta))$ ((7))

For a minimum: $2\pi/\text{wavelength} d \sin(\theta) = \pi + 2n\pi$ or:

$d \sin(\theta) = \text{wavelength} (n + 0.5)$ ((8))

For a maximum, one finds: $d \sin(\theta) = \text{wavelength} * n$ ((9))

As a result, one may mathematically solve this problem using $\exp(ipx)$, but we ask: What about the notion of p involved in an interaction which we discussed in the previous paragraph?

(px) and an Interaction

If one considers $\exp(ipx)$ as linked to an interaction, then for the two slit case, the momentum portion involved should be (px) , the x component of p , because the slits lie along the x axis. The distance considered is d (the separation of the slits).

Thus, we suggest that for quantum effects to appear:

$(px) d = 2\pi$ ((10))

In other words, (px) is associated with a wavelength representing x uncertainty and if an interaction contains this uncertainty length, quantum effects should appear.

Now: $(px) = p \sin(\theta) \rightarrow 2\pi/d = 2\pi/\text{wavelength} \sin(\theta) \rightarrow \text{wavelength} = d \sin(\theta)$ ((11))

Thus, the interaction view gives the first maximum result. The approach of the previous paragraph may be used to obtain the exact solution, but if one wishes to see the interaction physics linked with (px) , then the above approximation seems to show these. (In other words,

$\exp(ipx)$ is a math formalism used for calculations, but we suggest that there is also a physical viewpoint present.) In particular, the c signals are linked with momentum associated with a specific interaction. Here the both slits may interact because of the wavelength yielding x uncertainty, but a momentum hit is along the x direction and one must use (px) .

In some cases, one sees ((10)) listed in the literature as an example of the Heisenberg uncertainty principle for a free particle: $\Delta p \Delta x = \hbar$. (The full uncertainty principle is $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar/2$.)

Here, however, we consider ((10)) in terms of an interaction scheme and stress that $\exp(ipx)$ or $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ be considered in terms of specific momentum interactions as done in ((10)).

Conclusion

We consider the two slit interference problem using $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ formalism (which is the traditional approach) and leads to the usual equations. We argue that $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ should be associated with a physical viewpoint (and not just a calculation approach). We argue that p in $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ is associated with the overall momentum of a specific interaction. For example, if a photon with momentum p_1 approaches a moving 2-slit apparatus, p_1 is not the total momentum and this problem should be solved in the rest frame of the moving 2-slit apparatus. Thus, $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ is very much linked with momentum interactions.

In the case of 2-slit apparatus along the x axis with a p along the y , we argue that $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ is linked with signals (travelling at speed c) which are associated with an interaction. The interaction occurs along the x axis and so one should be interested in (px) (the x component of p) of the particle as this is the component which interacts. In order to see quantum effects, we suggest that: $(px) d = 2 \cdot 3.14$, i.e. the interaction length or resolution should match that of the interaction portion of p . Given that $p \sin(\theta) = (px)$ one obtains: $d \sin(\theta) = \text{wavelength}$ which matches the $n=1$ solution of a maxima. For a full solution, one should use the $\exp(ip \cdot r)$ approach, but we suggest that for a physical interpretation, one may consider (px) which is the interacting momentum component and deal with its lack of resolution matching d , the slit separation for an approximate solution.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Double-slit_experiment